

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

[Scientific articles]

SPOKE 5 – Industry of Health and Silver Economy

DELIVERABLE DN 9.4

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	12.01.2026	Publication within the project	Simona Rolla, Paola Costelli
0.5			
0.9			
1			

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

Contents

GLOSSARY	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
A) TITOLO SEZIONE.....	ERRORE. IL SEGNALIBRO NON È DEFINITO.
TITOLO PARAGRAFO.....	ERRORE. IL SEGNALIBRO NON È DEFINITO.
TITOLO PARAGRAFO.....	ERRORE. IL SEGNALIBRO NON È DEFINITO.
<i>Titolo Sub Paragrafo</i>	<i>Errore. Il segnalibro non è definito.</i>
<i>Titolo Sub Paragrafo</i>	<i>Errore. Il segnalibro non è definito.</i>
<i>Nuovo paragrafo controllo</i>	<i>Errore. Il segnalibro non è definito.</i>

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The RM9 aimed to develop tools useful to improve aging-associated sarcopenia by stimulating muscle

regeneration and targeting mitochondrial function, both aspects being frequently impaired in the elderly, together with identify a 'sarcopenia signature' in populations at risk. In addition to laboratory-based research, the activity also included literature reviews, which led to the publication of the following papers:

1) doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2023.1176016

The image shows a screenshot of a scientific article page from Frontiers in Immunology. The article title is "Feeding the gut microbiome: impact on multiple sclerosis". The authors listed are Matteo Bronzini, Alessandro Maglione, Rachele Rosso, Manuela Matta, Federica Masuzzo, Simona Rolla, and Marinella Clerico. The article is a review published on 25 May 2023. The abstract discusses the multifactorial nature of Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and the impact of diet on the gut microbiome. The introduction section is also visible, starting with "Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a neurological disease characterized by inflammation and immune-driven demyelination of the central nervous system (CNS)".

frontiers | Frontiers in Immunology

TYPE Review
PUBLISHED 25 May 2023
DOI 10.3389/fimmu.2023.1176016

Check for updates

OPEN ACCESS

EDITED BY
Gisiane Leles Vilela de Oliveira,
São Paulo State University, Brazil

REVIEWED BY
George Grant,
University of Aberdeen, United Kingdom
Vladimir Stanislavovich Rogovskii,
Pirogov Russian National Research Medical
University, Russia

*CORRESPONDENCE
Simona Rolla
✉ simona.rolla@unito.it

[†]These authors have contributed equally to this work and share first authorship

[‡]These authors share senior authorship

RECEIVED 28 February 2023
ACCEPTED 02 May 2023
PUBLISHED 25 May 2023

CITATION
Bronzini M, Maglione A, Rosso R, Matta M,
Masuzzo F, Rolla S and Clerico M (2023)
Feeding the gut microbiome: impact on
multiple sclerosis.
Front. Immunol. 14:1176016.
doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2023.1176016

COPYRIGHT
© 2023 Bronzini, Maglione, Rosso, Matta,
Masuzzo, Rolla and Clerico. This is an open-
access article distributed under the terms of
the Creative Commons Attribution License
(CC BY). The use, distribution or
reproduction in other forums is permitted,
provided the original author(s) and the
copyright owner(s) are credited and that
the original publication in this journal is
cited, in accordance with accepted
academic practice. No use, distribution or
reproduction is permitted which does not
comply with these terms.

KEYWORDS
multiple sclerosis, diet, gut microbiota, immune system, probiotics, prebiotics, postbiotics

1 Introduction

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a neurological disease characterized by inflammation and immune-driven demyelination of the central nervous system (CNS) (1). MS affects 2.5 million people worldwide (2) and is a major cause of progressive disability in young adults in Europe (3), with a higher prevalence in women (women/men ratio of ~2–3:1) (4). MS exists in several forms, with each form characterized by different disease progression and disability manifestations. The most common form of MS is relapsing–remitting MS (RRMS), which is characterized by the alternation of inflammatory acute phases, called relapses, and periods of remission (5). In general, several years after RRMS onset, most patients can develop a secondary progressive form of the disease (secondary progressive MS, SPMS), which is characterized by clinical deterioration, independent of relapses. In a minor proportion of subjects, MS can manifest in a chronic onset as primary progressive MS (PPMS) (6). The pathogenesis of MS is characterized by the presence of pro-inflammatory self-reactive T cells, mainly T-helper 1 (Th1), Th17, and Th22 cells,

Frontiers in Immunology 01 frontiersin.org

2. doi: 10.1007/s11914-024-00866-2

Current Osteoporosis Reports (2024) 22:257–265
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11914-024-00866-2>

Extracellular Vesicles and Exosomes in the Control of the Musculoskeletal Health

Fabio Penna¹ · Lorena Garcia-Castillo¹ · Paola Costelli¹

Accepted: 21 February 2024 / Published online: 1 March 2024
© The Author(s) 2024

Abstract

Purpose of Review The present review will highlight recent reports supporting the relevance of extracellular vesicles to the musculoskeletal system in health and disease.

Recent Findings Preserving the health of the musculoskeletal system is important to maintain a good quality of life, and the bone-muscle crosstalk is crucial in this regard. This latter is largely mediated by extracellular vesicles released by the different cell populations residing in muscle and bone, which deliver cargoes, microRNAs, and proteins being the most relevant ones, to target cells. Extracellular vesicles could be exploited as therapeutic tools, in view of their resistance to destruction in the biological fluid and of the possibility to be functionalized according to the need.

Summary Extracellular vesicles are recognized as crucial players in the bone-muscle cross-talk. Additional studies however are required to refine their use as biomarkers of early alterations of the musculoskeletal system, and as potential therapeutic tools.

Keywords Muscle-bone cross-talk · Sarcopenia · Bone loss · MicroRNAs · Therapeutic tools

Introduction

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) mediate the intercellular exchange of classical soluble and insoluble signaling factors, as well as of structural proteins, nucleic acids, and lipids. When released from the cell of origin, EVs travel through the interstitial space to reach the circulation. They can be uptaken by distant tissues, where they convey information able to affect the target cell function and/or metabolism and that could ultimately result in the production of other EVs that could go back to the initial source, in a sort of feedback mechanism. On the basis of their origin, size, physical properties, and functions, different types of EVs have been described, among which exosomes and microvesicles (MVs). Exosomes (50–150 nm) form within the intraluminal vesicles that are generated in the multivesicular bodies as part of the late endosomes. Multivesicular bodies can either fuse with lysosomes for degradation or travel back to and fuse with the plasma membrane. Thus, molecules can be

recycled and released into the extracellular space by means of exosomes. Sorting of the cargo during the internal budding of the membrane that leads to intraluminal vesicle formation is an essential step in exosome biogenesis [1]. By contrast, MV (50–1000 nm) generation starts from the formation of outward buds in specific sites of the plasma membrane followed by fission and subsequent release of the vesicle into the extracellular space. Lipid raft domains seem to be abundant in MVs, and MV formation can be impaired by cholesterol depletion. In addition to rearrangements in the plasma membrane composition, proteins responsible for cell shape maintenance may be involved in MV biogenesis [1].

EVs can be secreted by many cell types, including tumor cells. EV content is highly heterogeneous, consisting, in variable proportions, of proteins, DNA, microRNAs (miRs), mRNAs, lipids, surface molecules, etc. Importantly, EVs might represent a vehicle in which nucleic acids can be preserved and analyzed in biological fluids, as well as delivered to their target cells without being degraded in the extracellular space [1]. Due to these features, EVs have been proposed to work as biomarkers [2] and to be exploited as suitable therapeutic tools [3].

Several lines of evidence showed that EVs play a crucial role in the regulation of tissue homeostasis in health and in

✉ Paola Costelli
paola.costelli@unito.it

¹ Department of Clinical and Biological Sciences, University of Turin, Corso Raffaello 30, 10125 Turin, Italy

Article

Oleocanthal Protects C2C12 Myotubes against the Pro-Catabolic and Anti-Myogenic Action of Stimuli Able to Induce Muscle Wasting *In Vivo*

Daniela De Stefanis, Andrea Balestrini and Paola Costelli *

Department of Clinical and Biological Sciences, University of Turin, 10125 Turin, Italy; daniela.destefanis@unito.it (D.D.S.); andre.bale96@gmail.com (A.B.)

* Correspondence: paola.costelli@unito.it

Abstract: Oleocanthal (OC) is a monophenol of extra-virgin olive oil (EVOO) endowed with antibiotic, cardioprotective and anticancer effects, among others, mainly in view of its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. OC has been largely investigated in terms of its anticancer activity, in Alzheimer disease and in collagen-induced arthritis; however, the possibility that it can also affect muscle biology has been totally overlooked so far. This study is the first to describe that OC modulates alterations induced in C2C12 myotubes by stimuli known to induce muscle wasting *in vivo*, namely TNF- α , or in the medium conditioned by the C26 cachexia-inducing tumor (CM-C26). C2C12 myotubes were exposed to CM-C26 or TNF- α in the presence or absence of OC for 24 and 48 h and analyzed by immunofluorescence and Western blotting. In combination with TNF- α or CM-C26, OC was revealed to be able to restore both the myotube's original size and morphology and normal levels of both atrogin-1 and MuRF1. OC seems unable to impinge on the autophagic-lysosomal proteolytic system or protein synthesis. Modulations towards normal levels of the expression of molecules involved in myogenesis, such as Pax7, myogenin and MyHC, were also observed in the myotube cultures exposed to OC and TNF- α or CM-C26. In conclusion, the data presented here show that OC exerts a protective action in C2C12 myotubes exposed to TNF- α or CM-C26, with mechanisms likely involving the downregulation of ubiquitin-proteasome-dependent proteolysis and the partial relief of myogenic differentiation impairment.

Keywords: muscle wasting; TNF- α ; cachexia; tumor-conditioned medium; myogenesis

Citation: De Stefanis, D.; Balestrini, A.; Costelli, P. Oleocanthal Protects C2C12 Myotubes against the Pro-Catabolic and Anti-Myogenic Action of Stimuli Able to Induce Muscle Wasting *In Vivo*. *Nutrients* 2024, 16, 1302. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu16091302>

Academic Editor: Elad Tako

Received: 2 April 2024
Revised: 19 April 2024
Accepted: 23 April 2024
Published: 26 April 2024

Copyright © 2024 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Extra-virgin olive oil (EVOO), the main source of fat in the Mediterranean diet, contains several bioactive molecules, among which are phenols such as tyrosol, hydroxytyrosol, oleacein, ligsitroside glycone and oleocanthal (OC). They appear to exert antibiotic, cardioprotective, and anticancer effects, among others, mainly in view of their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties [1,2].

OC is a monophenol belonging to the category of secoiridoids which has been largely investigated in terms of its anticancer activity [3]. Indeed, data obtained using different cancer cell lines have shown that it impinges on the number of cells by inhibiting proliferation and inducing apoptosis [4]. Similar observations have been reported in experimental models of liver, breast and lung cancer [5]. Another study reported that an EVOO extract enriched with OC could potentiate the cytotoxic action of the pro-inflammatory cytokine TNF α on liver cancer cell lines [6]. In addition, OC was also reported to exert beneficial effects in experimental models of Alzheimer disease [7] and collagen-induced arthritis [8]. Up to now, there have been very few clinical trials aimed at investigating the beneficial effects of OC in human beings [5,9].

Polyphenols such as resveratrol, curcumin and epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG) have been proposed to positively act on muscle homeostasis, particularly when it is altered

Review

Immunomodulation: A new approach to cancer cachexia, potentially suitable for aging

Fabio Penna, Giacomo Rubini, Paola Costelli*

Department of Clinical and Biological Sciences, University of Turin, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Cachexia
Aging
Immune response
Muscle wasting
Sarcopenia
Immunomodulation

ABSTRACT

Cancer cachexia is the prototypical example of comorbidity, occurring in most of cancer patients. It is a direct consequence of tumor growth and of the associated inflammatory/immune response. Cachexia can be exacerbated by anti-cancer therapies, frequently resulting in dose limitation and/or treatment delay or discontinuation. The pathogenesis of cancer cachexia is still unclear and includes nutritional, metabolic, hormonal and immunological components.

Tumor ability to shape the immune response to its own advantage is now well accepted, while the possibility that such an altered immune response could play a role in the onset of cachexia is still an undefined issue. Indeed, most of the immune-related research on cachexia mainly focused on pro-inflammatory mediators, almost totally disregarding the interactions among immune cells and the homeostasis of peripheral tissues. The present review provides an overview of the immune system dysregulations occurring in cancer cachexia, focusing on the possibility that immunomodulating strategies, mainly developed to stimulate the anti-cancer immune response, could be useful to counteract cachexia as well.

Cancer and cachexia are frequent comorbidities of aging. Along this line, cancer- and aging-associated muscle wasting likely coexist in the same patients. Since both conditions share some of the underlying mechanisms, the potential effectiveness of immunomodulation on sarcopenia of aging is discussed.

The management of cancer patients is very frequently complicated by paraneoplastic syndromes, among which cachexia is one of the most relevant. By an international consensus cachexia has been defined as a complex multifactorial syndrome characterized by involuntary body weight loss and skeletal muscle wasting, associated or not with reduced adipose tissue mass, that can be only partially counteracted by nutritional approaches and eventually results in functional impairment (Fearon et al., 2011). According to the currently accepted definition, three phases of cachexia can be identified: pre-cachexia, cachexia, and refractory cachexia. Patient progression through these three levels depends on several extrinsic and intrinsic factors (Fearon et al., 2011).

The prevalence of cachexia among cancer patients is markedly high, although considerable differences can be observed according to tumor type and disease stage (Anker et al., 2019). The management of cancer patients with cachexia is very complicated, due to their poor quality of life associated with reduced tolerance and response to treatments, which eventually result in increased death rates (Roeland et al., 2020). Along this line, about 90% of cancer patients are at risk of developing cachexia, with a mortality rate that can reach 80%/year (von Haehling et al.,

2016). Unfortunately, despite its relevance to cancer patient outcome, this syndrome is still largely unrecognized and underdiagnosed. In addition, at present no specific therapies for cachexia are available, mainly due to the lack of data from appropriate pre-clinical and clinical studies supporting new pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions. The more so, pre-clinical studies frequently overlook the side-effects exerted by anticancer treatments, that further exacerbate whole body wasting (Campelj et al., 2021).

1. Pathogenesis of cachexia

The pathogenetic mechanisms underlying cancer cachexia are only partially elucidated, although the multifactorial nature of this syndrome is now well recognized, including nutritional, metabolic, hormonal and immunological components.

Malnutrition, a frequent occurrence in cancer patients, is predictive of bad outcome. In this regard, patients should be nutritionally assessed as soon as possible during the course of the disease. Indeed, cancer can impinge very early on dietary habits in view of mechanisms directly

* Corresponding author. Dept. of Clinical and Biological Sciences, University of Turin, Corso Raffaello 30, 10125, Torino, Italy.
E-mail address: paola.costelli@unito.it (P. Costelli).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mam.2024.101318>

Received 2 February 2024; Received in revised form 18 July 2024; Accepted 5 September 2024

Available online 10 September 2024

0098-2997/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

REVIEW

Mechanisms Underlying Diversity in Cancer Cachexia

Inflammation in cancer cachexia: still the central tenet or just another player?

● Noemi Iala,^{1,2*} ● Chiara Novello,^{1,2*} Maurizio Muscaritoli,³ and ● Paola Costelli^{1,2}

¹Department of Clinical and Biological Sciences, University of Turin, Turin, Italy; ²Department of Translational Medicine, University of Eastern Piedmont, Novara, Italy; and ³Department of Translational Medicine, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy

Abstract

Cancer cachexia, a multifactorial syndrome characterized by body weight loss, muscle, and adipose tissue wasting, affects patients with cancer. Over time, the definition of cachexia has been modified, including inflammation as one of the main causal factors. Evidence has suggested that a range of proinflammatory mediators may be involved in the regulation of intracellular signaling, resulting in enhanced resting energy expenditure, metabolic changes, and muscle atrophy, all of which are typical features of cachexia. Physiologically speaking, however, inflammation is a response aimed at facing potentially damaging events. Along this line, its induction in the cancer hosts could be an attempt to restore the physiological homeostasis. Interesting observations have shown that cytokines such as interleukins 4 and 6 could improve muscle wasting, supporting the view that the same mediator may exert pro- or anti-inflammatory activity depending on the immune cells involved as well as on the tissue metabolic demand. In conclusion, whether inflammation is crucial to the occurrence of cachexia or just one contributor among others, is still unclear. Indeed, while inflammation is a trigger of cachexia, the alterations of energy and protein metabolism and of the hormonal homeostasis occurring in cachexia likely act as inflammatory stimuli on their own. Whether the causative role prevails over the compensatory one likely depends on the tumor type and stage, patient lifestyle, the presence of comorbidities, and the response to anticancer treatments paving the way to a holistic, personalized approach to cancer cachexia.

cachexia; cancer; cytokines; inflammation; skeletal muscle

The International Agency for Research on Cancer estimated that in 2022, 19,976,499 cases of cancer were diagnosed globally and ~10 million people died from the disease. Furthermore, a study published in the last year evidenced that the global incidence and morbidity of early-onset cancer increased by 27.7% and 79.1%, respectively, from 1990 to 2019 (1). Such growing global burden makes prevention of cancer one of the most significant public health challenges of the 21st century (<https://www.wcrf.org/cancer-trends/worldwide-cancer-data/>). Progression of most solid cancers is complicated by the occurrence of a clinical syndrome known as cachexia, mainly characterized by anorexia, unintentional body weight loss, inflammation, insulin resistance, and increased muscle protein breakdown. Specifically, up to 80% of cancer cases are associated with this syndrome, leading to a decrease in both quality of life and overall survival. The incidence of cachexia varies depending on the tumor type, being rather low (~20%) in patients affected by breast or prostate cancer, but progressively increases moving to hematological malignancies (40%–50%) and to tumors of the digestive tract (60%–70%) (2).

The occurrence of cachexia markedly complicates the management of patients with cancer, with the poor quality of life being associated with increased toxicity of the anticancer treatments (3). In addition to the lack of specific approved pharmacological tools to address cachexia, this syndrome is frequently diagnosed late in the cancer journey, reducing the possibility of setting up interventions aimed at slowing down its progression. To overcome such a late recognition, in the past two decades, researchers in the field put an effort into coining a definition of cachexia, which has evolved over time, also following the advances in mechanistic knowledge. A brief description of such evolution is provided here as follows:

- 2006. Arends et al. (4) published the European Society for Clinical Nutrition and Metabolism (ESPEN) Guidelines on Enteral Nutrition: Nonsurgical oncology, where cachexia was described as the result of “systemic proinflammatory processes in response to the tumor,” characterized by an acute phase response and associated with metabolic alterations affecting both fat and muscle compartments.

*N. Iala and C. Novello contributed equally to this work.

Correspondence: P. Costelli (paola.costelli@unito.it).

Submitted 6 November 2024 / Revised 23 November 2024 / Accepted 10 April 2025

<http://www.ajpcell.org>

0363-6143/25 Copyright © 2025 The Authors. Licensed under Creative Commons Attribution CC-BY-NC 4.0.
Published by the American Physiological Society.

C1837

Downloaded from journals.physiology.org/journal/ajpcell at Univ Studi Di Torino Bib Ctral Di Med E (130.192.098.151) on January 12, 2026.